

CALCULATION OF SELF-STARTING CURRENTS OF ELECTRIC MOTORS

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doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11179280

Annotation: The article discusses a method for calculating the possibility of self-starting an asynchronous motor during a power outage. The purpose of this is to identify and provide conditions for the automatic restart of an asynchronous motor in order to ensure dynamic stability. An analysis of the stage of successful self-start of an electrical network and an asynchronous motor using equivalent circuits was carried out. When determining self-starting currents, failure to take into account the influence of the ratio of currents in the branches can lead to significant errors in determining self-starting currents and residual voltages on the buses. The ratio of currents in the reactor branches is not known in advance since the currents in the branches themselves are subject to determination. Therefore, it is impossible to determine the resistances of the reactor branches before calculating the currents. This paper discusses the calculation of self-starting currents and residual voltages without first determining the ratio of currents in the branches during the self-starting of electric motors at a pumping station after power restoration.

Keywords: self-starting, asynchronous motor, reactor, residual voltage, power supply, branch currents, short circuit current, equivalent circuit, mutual induction resistance, residual speed.

Today, in the development of the industrial complex, close attention is paid to increasing the level of electrification as well as the automation of technological, main, and auxiliary production processes. To perform the required tasks, it is necessary to ensure an increase in the power of the electric motors used and the widespread introduction of automated electric drives. Solving the assigned tasks leads to the organization and development of the technological process, but also to a simultaneous strengthening of their interdependence, which aggravates the consequences of emergency conditions. Such modes are associated with disruptions in the power supply of industrial enterprises. Consequently, the development of issues related to the electric drive should be associated with emergency conditions in the power supply system [1,2].

This paper discusses the calculation of self-starting currents and residual voltages without first determining the ratio of currents in the branches during the self-starting of electric motors at a pumping station after power restoration. If there is a loss of power from transformer T1 (Figure 1), the input switches of the first (1SHC) and second (2SS) bus sections are turned off. With a certain time delay, the automatic transfer switch devices (ASR) are activated, the section switches are turned on, and ED1 of the first bus section will receive power from the third (3ss) section of tires. To simplify the analysis, it is assumed that the electric motors ED2 and ED3 are turned off and ED4 in the fourth bus section is turned on, and when the transformer T1 was turned off, it remained under load. The power interruption time can be several seconds. During this time, ED1, running out, slows down to a certain residual speed and, when the sectional switch is turned on, finds itself in self-starting mode at a certain residual

speed [3, 4].

Fig. 1 - Power supply diagram of the pumping station

A feature of a dual reactor is the presence of magnetic coupling (mutual inductance M) between the branches of each phase. The degree of inductive coupling of the windings is characterized by the coupling coefficient, which is specified in the reactor datasheet:

$$K_{sv} = \frac{M}{\sqrt{L_1 \cdot L_2}} = \frac{M}{L} \tag{1}$$

where M is the mutual inductance of the reactor branches; L=L1=L2 is the self-inductance of each branch. The network replacement diagram after the ASR is triggered is shown in Fig. 2, where the dual reactor is represented by a two-beam equivalent circuit. The direction of the EDS vectors is shown for the worst case, namely, for asynchronous switching, when the mains voltage and the EDS of the motor ED1 are in antiphase.

Let us represent the resistance of each branch as the sum of two resistances: the nominal resistance of the reactor X_n and the resistance of mutual induction. This

representation of the reactor resistance allows us to avoid the dependence of the resistance on the ratio of currents in the branches.

$$X_{M1} = X_{M2} = K_{CB} \cdot X_H \tag{2}$$

The mutual induction resistance for each branch of the reactor is equal to

For clarity, the equivalent circuit in Fig. 2 is presented in the form of a two-circuit diagram (Fig. 3), where I_1 is the current in the first branch (or the current in self-starting ED1), I_2 is the current in the second branch (or the current generated by ED4), and I_3 is the current in the third branch (or the current in the supply network to the reactor) [5, 6, 7].

Rice. 3 - Converted equivalent circuit.

The currents in the circuit in Fig. 3 are easily determined by one of the methods for calculating alternating current circuits, for example, the loop current method.

In this case, taking into account (1), we obtain the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} I_{11} \cdot (2 \cdot X_n + 2 \cdot X_n \cdot K_{sv} + X_{d1}'' + X_{d2}'') + I_{22} \cdot (X_n \cdot K_{sv} + X_{d2}'' + X_n) \\ = E_{d1}'' + E_{d2}'', \end{cases}$$

$$I_{11} \cdot (X_n \cdot K_{sv} + X_{d2}'' + X_n) + I_{22} \cdot (X_{d2}'' + X_n + X_s') = E_{d2}'' - U_s$$

The residual EMF E''_{d1} at the moment of switching on will have a frequency equal to the residual rotation speed of the electric motor, which in the general case is not equal to synchronous. However, when calculating the turn-on currents and residual voltages at the moment the sectional switch is turned on, the values of currents and voltages are of interest only at the first moment in time, without taking into account changes in their values over time. Therefore, in the practice of calculations, different frequencies of the network voltage and EDS E''_{d1} are usually not taken into account. The supertransient EDS E''_{d2} depends on the load of the motor ED4.

$$E''_{d2} = \sqrt{(I_{(0)} \cdot X_{d2}'' \cdot \cos\varphi_{(0)})^2 + (U_{(0)} + I_{(0)} \cdot X_{d2}'' \cdot \sin\varphi_{(0)})^2} \tag{4}$$

where I is the current in the previous mode; $U_{(0)}$: voltage in the previous mode; $\varphi_{(0)}$: angle between current and voltage in the same mode; X''_{d2} : supertransient inductive reactance ED4.

According to the condition of permissibility of self-starting, the operating setting of the device for automatically turning on the sectional switch is selected according to the value of E''_{d1} . When calculating self-starting, it is necessary to find a value of E''_{d1} at which the self-starting current (current I_1 in Fig. 3) will be acceptable. This is done by repeatedly solving system (3) with the subsequent construction of the relationship between current I_1 and emf E''_{d1} .

- for the power system in maximum mode.
- - - - - for the power system in minimum mode.

Rice. 4 : Dependence of the non-synchronous switching current on the value of the residual EDS ED1

As an example, self-starting at a pumping station was calculated. The graph of the dependence of the self-starting current on the value of the residual EDS ED1 is shown in Fig. 4. The permissible switching current is $1.08 K_p$, where K_p is a multiple of the starting current. With a starting current factor of 7.0, the permissible switching current factor will be $K_{dop} = 7.56$. From Figure 4, it follows that the permissible current multiplicity $K_{dop} = 7.56$ corresponds to the maximum permissible value of the residual EMF $E_{dop} = 0.49$. The advantages of calculating self-starting currents and residual voltages without converting the equivalent circuit to an equivalent (reduced) form are:

1. It is not necessary to determine the resistance of the branches of a dual reactor depending on the ratio of currents in the branches.
2. the ability to take into account the transition of electric motors that have not lost power to generator mode due to a voltage drop when the sectional switch is turned on;
3. It becomes possible to plot the dependence of the self-starting current (switch-on current) on the permissible value of the residual EDS and evaluate the

permissible value of the residual voltage on the busbars for different parameters of electric motors.

References

1. Venikov, V.A. Transient processes of electrical systems in examples and illustrations Ed. Venikova V.A. M.L.: Energy, 1968, S. 238.
2. Venikov V.A., Transient electromechanical processes in electrical systems. Higher. School, 1978, S. 122-125.
3. Golodnov, Y.M. Self-starting of electric motors. M.: Energoatomizdat, 1985, S. 84.
4. Zhdanov P.S., Issues of Stability of Electrical Systems, Energy, 1979, S. 232-234.
5. Kulikov, Y.A. Transient processes in electrical systems: textbook, manual. Novosibirsk: NSTU PublishingHouse, 2003. S. 124-200.